

Preparation and Use of Membrane Electrodes of Acid Salts of Esterified Proteins for Determination of Anion Activities of Electrolytic Solutions. Part I. Denatured Ovalbumin

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Film membranes, 0.6 to 1.0 mm thick, of hydrochloride of methanol-esterified, denatured ovalbumin have been prepared and the portions showing zero asymmetric potential used for determining the membrane potential, using saturated calomel electrodes. With KCl solutions having Cl^- ion molarity ratio of 2.25 at the same pH on the two sides, the membrane potential has been found to be the same at different pHs from 3.6 to 7.5.

Cl^- ion of the membrane could be exchanged for any other anion; the respective membranes have been used for determining anion activities of HCl, KCl, KBr, KI, and KNO_3 solutions in the ranges of concentrations: (1) 0.0015 to 0.025 M ; (2) 0.0015 to 0.0186 M ; (3) 0.00075 to 0.0125 M , with the molarity ratios of 2, 3, and 4 respectively, the observed membrane potential agreeing with that calculated from the Nernst equation. The experimental error in the membrane potential is within $\pm 2.0\%$ and that in the activity ratio, within $\pm 1.5\%$.

Jacobson¹ described a synthetic ampholyte membrane formed from the monomers, methacrylic acid and *N*-diethylamino-2-ethyl methacrylate containing weakly acidic and basic groups; its membrane potential was negative at lower pH from 4.0 to 5.5, increased continuously with pH, was zero at the isoelectric pH 6.1, and became positive at pH 6.2, increasing continuously up to pH 7.5. The hydrochloride of denatured ovalbumin was found by the authors to behave in the same manner, the membrane potential being zero at the isoelectric pH 5.2.

The object of the present work is to prepare film membranes from the hydrochloride of methanol-esterified, denatured ovalbumin, expecting it to work as an anion exchanger with no ampholytic properties; since the $-\text{COO}^-$ group is converted into $-\text{CO}_2\text{Me}$ group and the $-\text{NH}_3^+$ group to $-\text{NH}_3^+ \text{Cl}^-$, Cl^- ion could be exchanged with any other anion by soaking the membrane in 1*N* solution of a salt containing the required anion. Such an esterified film membrane is expected to be useful in the determination of anion activities in dilute solutions of electrolytes in the same manner as those of synthetic anion exchangers, used by Sinha², Basu³⁻⁴, and others.

EXPERIMENTAL

Isoelectric crystalline ovalbumin was prepared from fresh eggs of a hen by the method suggested by Kechwick and Cannon⁵. Sodium sulphate was removed by washing with

1. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1962, **66**, 570.
2. *This Journal*, 1954, **31**, 577; 1953, **30**, 529.
3. *Science & Culture*, 1956, **21**, 447.
4. *This Journal*, 1962, **39**, 619.
5. *Biochem. J.*, 1936, **30**, 232.

acetone, which denatured the protein at the same time. The denatured ovalbumin (10 g.) was esterified with methanol (200 ml), containing 0.1 g. equiv. of HCl per litre, by keeping for 7 days with repeated shaking, as suggested by Frankel *et al*⁶. Due to presence of HCl, the hydrochloride of esterified denatured ovalbumin was formed, as was tested by ion-exchange method after washing with CO₂-free distilled water. The filtered and washed mass of the protein salt was dried between filter paper pads. The film membranes were prepared from it by placing semidry powder between filter paper pads in a small cylindrical metal box (with a false bottom), fitted with a piston, and pressing in a screw press, the pressure being maintained for 48 hours. The films thus formed were dried in a vacuum desiccator for 48 hours and then their thickness was determined. The films were soaked in 0.1*N*-HCl for 24 hours to make them swell, so as to facilitate the membrane material to ionise. The films were then washed with CO₂-free distilled water and preserved in distilled water containing a crystal of thymol to prevent fungus growth. For using the film as a membrane electrode, it was fitted between two rubber washers to the end of a glass tube (diam. 1 cm) on which an insulated cap could be screwed up.

The membrane potential was measured with the help of saturated calomel electrodes by placing electrolytic solutions of different ionic strengths inside and outside the tube. For the first measurement, 45 minutes were allowed to equilibrate, after which subsequent measurements were made after an interval of 15 minutes. The E.M.F. readings remained constant for more than half an hour. The E.M.F. measurements were made with the help of a Cambridge potentiometer, reading between 0.01 and 20.0 mv and from 0.05 and 100.0 mv, the null-point instrument being a ballistic mirror galvanometer. The asymmetric potential was found by placing 0.1*N*-KCl on both the sides; those films which provided zero asymmetry potential were used for subsequent experiments. All measurements were made at 25°.

For studying the influence of *pH* on the membrane potential, KCl solutions of ionic strengths 0.02 and 0.01, adjusted to the same *pH*, were used on the two sides of the membrane; the *pH* values 3.6 to 5.5 were adjusted with potassium acetate-acetic acid buffers and *pH* 6.0 to 7.5 with KH₂PO₄-K₂HPO₄ buffers, preparing first solutions of 0.2 and 0.1 ionic strengths according to Conway⁷ and then diluting the both ten times with CO₂-free distilled water. The *pH* of the solutions to be used on the two sides of the membrane was found to be the same by the Cambridge *pH*-meter. The concentration of the buffers, and hence the activities of the acetate or the phosphate ions on both sides of the membrane being the same, the E.M.F. due to other anions cancelled out, whereas that due to difference of Cl⁻ ion on the two sides was measured. The results are recorded in Table I.

For the determination of activities of various anions, the Cl⁻ ion was exchanged for other ions by repeated soaking of the film membrane from 24 to 72 hours in 1*N* solution of the salts containing these anions. The results of anion-activity measurements with HCl, KCl, KBr, KI, KNO₃, and K₂SO₄ solution, using Film B (vide Table I) are recorded in Table II. For calculating the values of membrane potential according to the Nernst equation, the required activity data were obtained from Conway⁷ and Lewis and Randall⁸.

6. *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1945, 161, 259.

7. *Electro-chemical Data*, Elsevier Publishing Comp., New York, 1952.

8. *"Thermodynamics and Free Energy of Chemical Substances"*.

TABLE I

Influence of pH on the membrane potential.

- (1) Film (A) of hydrochloride of denatured ovalbumin: =1.6 mm thick.
 (2) Film (B) of hydrochloride of esterified denatured ovalbumin: 1.14 mm thick.

Molarity ratio.		pH.	Observed membrane potential.	
K ⁺ ions.	Cl ⁻ ions.		Film A.	Film B.
2.00	2.25	3.8	-16.40 mv	-16.70 mv
2.00	2.25	4.0	-16.00	-16.74
2.00	2.25	4.5	-12.03	-16.20
2.00	2.25	5.0	- 6.00	-16.20
2.00	2.25	5.5	+ 7.00	-15.90
2.02	2.25	6.0	+ 8.50	-15.90
2.04	2.25	6.5	+11.80	-16.70
2.05	2.25	7.0	+16.50	-16.40
2.08	2.25	7.5	+16.60	-16.20

TABLE II

	1. Electrolyte. 2. Molarity ratio. 3. Film thickness.	Anion activity of solutions.		Membrane potential (mv).	
		Inside. (+)	Outside. (-)	Obs.	Calc.
1.	HCl	0.00296	0.00146	18.00	18.10
2.	2:1	0.00583	0.00296	17.40	17.37
3.	1.15 mm	0.01143	0.00583	17.20	17.25
		0.02220	0.01143	17.10	17.02
		0.04250	0.02220	12.00	16.63
1.	KCl	0.00296	0.00146	18.00	18.10
2.	2:1	0.00583	0.00296	16.90	17.37
3.	1.6 mm	0.01143	0.00583	16.80	17.25
		0.02220	0.01143	17.00	17.02
		0.04250	0.02220	11.00	16.63
1.	KBr	0.00296	0.00146	18.00	18.10
2.	2:1	0.00583	0.00296	17.60	17.37
3.	1.6 mm	0.01143	0.00583	17.00	17.25
		0.02220	0.01143	17.00	17.02
		0.04250	0.02220	15.40	16.63
1.	KCl	0.00217	0.00074	28.00	27.71
2.	3:1	0.00427	0.00146	27.40	27.55
3.	0.899 mm	0.00861	0.00296	27.60	27.36
		0.01677	0.00583	26.40	27.08
		0.03251	0.01143	17.80	26.79
1.	KBr	0.00217	0.00074	27.00	27.71
2.	3:1	0.00426	0.00146	27.20	27.55
3.	0.899 mm	0.00861	0.00296	27.00	27.31
		0.01677	0.00583	26.60	27.08
		0.03251	0.01143	18.50	26.79

TABLE II (contd.)

1. Electrolyte. 2. Molarity ratio. 3. Film thickness.	Anion activity of solutions.		Membrane potential (mv).	
	Inside. (+)	Outside. (-)	Obs.	Calc.
1. KCl	0.00296	0.00073	36.00	35.63
2. 4:1	0.00583	0.00146	35.40	35.48
3. 0.898 mm	0.01143	0.00206	34.00	34.61
	0.02204	0.05830	29.00	34.08
1. KI	0.00290	0.00146	18.10	18.10
2. 2:1	0.00583	0.00296	17.50	17.37
3. 0.975 mm	0.01143	0.00583	17.00	17.25
	0.02220	0.01143	16.40	17.02
	0.04250	0.02220	12.00	16.63
1. KNO ₃	0.00206	0.00144	17.80	16.31
2. 2:1	0.00577	0.00206	17.06	17.14
3. 0.899 mm	0.01120	0.00577	17.06	17.00
	0.02132	0.01122	16.60	16.45
	0.03850	0.02132	10.15	15.15
1. K ₂ SO ₄	0.00121	0.00004	8.12	8.21
2. 2:1	0.00232	0.00121	8.20	8.20
3. 0.970 mm	0.00414	0.00232	8.00	7.43
	0.00733	0.00414	6.75	7.30
	0.01235	0.00733	3.20	6.67

DISCUSSION

The data recorded in Table I show that for the Film A, the observed negative potential decreases with pH, passes through zero at the isoelectric pH 6.1, and then becomes positive. This behaviour of the film is indicative of the ampholytic nature of denatured ovalbumin hydrochloride. The results agree with those obtained by Jacobson¹ in the case of synthetic polyampholyte.

On the other hand, the near constancy of membrane potential with pH observed with the esterified denatured ovalbumin film, using KCl solutions of ionic strengths 0.01 and 0.02, shows an almost complete blocking of -COOH group⁶. The slight change in the membrane potential with pH may be attributed to the swelling of the protein film with pH and consequent to change in the ionisation of the membrane. Therefore the film membrane of an acid salt of the esterified ovalbumin may be used for a satisfactory measurement of anion activities of electrolytic solutions. This is substantiated by the data recorded in Table II. The results show a fairly good agreement (within $\pm 2.0\%$) between the observed and the calculated values according to the Nernst equation. The range of validity is from 0.0015*M* to 0.025*M* for Cl⁻, Br⁻, I⁻, and NO₃⁻ ions with molarity ratio of 2, whereas for the same ions the range of validity is from 0.0015*M* to 0.0186*M* with molarity ratio 3, and 0.00075*M* to 0.0125*M* with ratio 4. In the case of K₂SO₄, there is an agreement between the observed and the calculated value for solutions within the range of 0.00075 to 0.0030*M*. At concentrations higher than these, lower E.M.F.s, similar to those observed by Sollner⁹ and Basu⁴, were recorded.